

Research Guidelines on Big Data and Data Analytics: A Survey

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OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Issue: 3

Month: Januray

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2321-788X

Received: 01.11.2018

Accepted: 03.01.2019

Published: 30.01.2019

Citation:

Vaishnavi, B., and C. Uma, V & Sunitha Ram. "Research Guidelines on Big Data and Data Analytics: A Survey." *Shanlax Internatioal Journal of Arts, Science and Humanities*, vol. 6, no. 3, 2019, pp. 7–17.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2550001>

Abstract

Large number of devices and objects are now linked to the internet, to transmit data, and collect data back for analytics. The goal is here to utilize this data to make a positive impact on our lifestyle, energy conservation, transportation, and health. The term "Big Data" existed before IoT arrived to carry out the analytics. The management of Big Data in a constantly expanding network gives rise to non-trivial concerns regarding data collection efficiency, data processing, analytics, and security. In this effort, therefore we carry out a survey on Big Data technologies in different domains to make easy and inspire knowledge sharing across different fields. Based on the review, this work discusses an overview, architecture, applications, challenges, techniques, methodologies, privacy and technologies, similarities and differences among Big Data technologies used in different domains, proposes how sure Big Data technology used in one realm can be re-used in an additional area, and develops an abstract framework to outline the Big Data technologies. Then a structure may be established based on the emerging innovation behind data and analytics, managing, exploring and enabling the challenges in different task leads to the evolution of Big Data and Analytics.

Keywords: Big Data, Big Data Analytics, Internet of Things.

Introduction

The term Big Data was coined under the explosive increase of global data and was mainly used to describe the enormous datasets. These datasets are compared with traditional datasets because it does not support real-time data [i.e., 15 unstructured data]. This leads to the evolution of Big Data [1].

In January 2007, Jim Gray, a pioneer of database software, called such transformation "The Fourth Paradigm" [2]. He also thought the only way to cope with such a paradigm was to develop a new generation of computing tools to manage, visualize, and analyze massive data. In June 2011, another milestone event occurred, when EMC/IDC published a research report titled Extracting Values from Chaos [3], which introduced the concept and potential of Big Data. This research report aroused great interest in both industry and academia on Big Data.

Big Data analytics [4] examines large amounts of data to uncover hidden patterns, correlations and other insights. Data-driven companies already using machine-generated data from the IoT to enhance customer service, generate more yields from new products and services, optimize data and feed more data into existing analytical efforts.

Datameer is a modern BI platform, an analytics solution that helps to turn massive volumes of machine-generated sensor data into valuable, timely insights that are powerful and yet simple for everyone to use. It runs natively on Hadoop, where we can aggregate all types of data in one place, regardless of its size.

TRUSTe[7] highlighted the fact that privacy concerns could be a significant barrier to the growth of IoT. According to the TRUSTe survey, about 60% of internet users have simple privacy awareness of IoT, and they know that smart devices, such as smart TVs, fitness devices, and in-car navigation systems could collect personal activities data. The following points are important while designing a gateway to the Big IoT data architecture. They are Rapid deployment and simple management. With the increment of new Big Data systems, the new demands on storing, analyzing, and processing different kinds of Big Data systems have specific goals, and it must be adopted by some specific usage patterns [8].

As a result, each of them exposes different interfaces, and the user must get confused to select which one is valuable for their situation. Without a flexible system for interface access and management, the applicability of the platform will be reduced much. To solve this difficult, a promising approach delivered to create a middle layer for each system to provide a unified interface [9]. However, this approach has some limitations experienced in Big Data platforms.

Minh Chau Nguyen et al. proposed a new architecture for the gateway-based access system to overcome the above challenges [10]. Knowledge discovery, pattern analysis and information harvesting are the terms which are often used by the researcher in Internet of Things world. The researcher used the word “polyglot persistence” concept, in the selection of database system in Big Data environment [12].

Several computing technologies are used in wireless sensor networks like Fog, Edge and Cloud are compared with one another. The core drive of this paper is to convey the researcher to see the surprising visions of BIG IoT Technology. This paper will be helpful for all the practitioners/researchers/academicians to choose their research

path in this field. The traditional RDBMS [Relational Data Base Management System] is not able to support heterogeneous data (i.e.,) unstructured data. All types of data including structured, semi-structured, and unstructured data - explored from the IoT devices were handled by this new Data Base Management System – “NoSQL [Not Only SQL]” is possible in this Big Data Platforms.

Related Research Work

C.L. Philip Chen and Chun-Yang Zhang (2014), provided detailed information about the Big Data with its technologies and the different problems faced by this Big Data for handling data in various fields such as business, administration, commerce and scientific research. It also provides evidence for the opportunity to use Big Data. One leading task for the researcher is the challenges faced by every step of the Big Data Process because which contains different techniques such as Mathematics tools, Data Analysis tools. Big Data applications are used to process information stored in the Big Data with the help of the following modes: -Batch Processing, Stream Processing and Interactive Analysis [1].

Kari Venkatram and Geetha Mary (2017), states that without analytics, there is no Big Data in this migration of technological period. Big Data characteristics are explained shortly using “V’s”, -Likewise data attributes are illuminated using 5C’s which are Clean, Consistent, Confirmed, Current and Comprehensive.

The NoSQL Data Base Structure stores all types of data including unstructured, semi-structured and structured data. It can be categorized based on the requirement we need, as follows: Key value store, Column-oriented database, Graph database, Document-oriented database. The term “Data Analytics” is a science used to draw insights out of the information from the data. And this analytics helps to improve the overall decision-making process in all the fields. It is divided by four types namely- Prescriptive, Predictive, Diagnostic and Descriptive. All the data are stored by Apache Hadoop architecture – A modules like a master and slave kind of architecture. Not only in Apache Hadoop, but also with Map reduces, Apache [Hive, Pig, Flume, Sqoop, Spark, Zookeeper] [4].

Ejaz Ahmed et al. (2017), the management of Big Data in a network of things arises some concern regarding data collection, efficiency, data processing, analytic, and security. All these are identified clearly when there is an examination made on the challenges associated with the deployment of IoT. The different group of researchers proposed the IoT based Big Data and analytics in diverse fields with some evidence. The requirements for Big Data and analytics in IoT have increased day- by- day. So there is a key – Connectivity, Storage, Quality of Service, Real-time analytics and Benchmark play a vital role in improving IoT services through this analytics.

The taxonomy of Big Data and analytic solutions for IoT systems are shown. It has the following attributes - Big Data sources, System components, Big Data enabling technologies, Functional elements, Analytics type. “The major sources of Big Data are IoT applications” – this statement clearly explain the relationship between IoT and Big Data. The current IoT environment provides opportunities for current Big Data and analytics. They are Decision making, Improved Efficiency, Independence from data silos, Value added applications [13].

Mohsen Marjani et al. (2017), proposed a new architecture for Big IoT data analytics, its methods and technologies for Big Data Mining. Use cases are also presented by researchers for easy understanding of – “How the applications are benefitted by this new technological improvement”. It discussed the existing analytical systems such as Real- time, Off-line, Memory-level, Business Intelligence ,and Massive analytics very efficiently. Generally, the deployment of IoT increases the amount of data in quantity and category, which in turn leads to the management of data (i.e.,) Big Data using some tools.

The Author explained about the Big Data IoT usecases (i.e.,) an application using some device. Here Six usecases are discussed based on its benefits and which IoT devices are used to capture data, which format the data hold [either video, audio, image, text ...] and what analytics platform is used to handle the data. Opportunities provided each field to make use of this new technology for easy decision making and better processing of data. Big IoT Data arise

with some challenges, even though they are solved to some extent but not fulfilled. Some issues may be tackled with the help of Data Mining techniques. Data Integration leads to a lack of tools to the management of data; this in turn leads to a complex process [11].

Sulayman K. Sowe et al. (2014) described an integrated IoT architecture with the supporting functionalities of SCN [Service Controlled Networking] in connection with Cloud Computing. The sensor data from various heterogeneous sources are managed using some protocols. The different layers present between Data-intensive research communities [i.e., end user] SCN Model is described 91 with its architecture. The integrated IoT architecture exhibits Cloud Service models as – IaaS [Infrastructure As A Service], PaaS [Platform As A Service], SDaaS [Data / Sensor Data As A Service], SaaS [Software As A Service]. This integrated architecture for managing Data-intensive research is depicted 92 with the Japan Gigabit Network (JGN-X) layer node, middleware, physical & virtual machine servers, engines, processors and APIs. Then one case study – PM 2.5 be discussed here as an example of combining our own created sensor data with the social sensor data. This PM 2.5 sensor data is analyzed using STICKER (Spatio Temporal Information Clustering and Knowledge Extraction) – a Big Data Visualization tool [14].

A. Shobanadevi and G. Maragatham (2017) - reviewed the existing techniques and algorithms for IoT implementation with Hadoop and Spark technology. Hybrid data mining algorithms using the Map Reduce framework are revised. Without Mining process, the Big Data will 97 no longer possible for the organizations. Previous mining process belongs to a single main memory. But with the tremendous amount of data Parallel Computing / Mining came into existence. Clusters of computing nodes are needed when we processed some Exabyte of data and this is possible with the deployment of some programming tools/ frameworks such as Map Reduce [15].

Perera C. Ranjan et al. describes the foremost objective of IoT is to learn more and more and to serve better to the system users. The real value of data collection comes from data processing and

aggregation on a large scale where new knowledge can be extracted by the user. This leads to user privacy issues, which are discussed by many researchers to produce their reports accordingly. TRUSTe highlighted the privacy concerns because it could be a significant barrier to the growth of IoT. Their survey revealed that 87% of internet users were concerned about the type of personal information collected. There are many challenges associated with privacy in the context of IoT which are explained here in a detailed way with some examples. They are User consent Acquisition, Control, customization and Freedom of Choice, Promise and Reality, Anonymity Technology, Security [16].

Minh Chau Nguyen et al. (2017), managing access interfaces is a chief process of analytic service development because more systems are connected to develop the process. This paper proposed a system with interface management to allow end –user to easily to do their desired functions including metadata and data access. So this system helps the platform managers, to extend and modify the access interfaces.

Multiple users belong to different fields use Big Data as a service platform. So the architecture designed here contained eight blocks including interface management. The architecture of Gateway-based Access Interface management concept is depicted well by the researchers and described well.

Case study – ETRI Big Data Platform implemented the gateway – based access interface management system is discussed by the researchers. Finally, it concluded that the system could mitigate the aftermath of the heterogeneity of the interfaces provided by the several organizations [12].

Hesham El-Sayed (2017), presented the survey on Edge systems and the comparative study with cloud computing systems with IoT. Fog and Multi–cloud computing advantages are discussed. The most important purpose of the proposed architecture is used to provide a better Quality- of- Experience [QOE] for end users with low response time and throughput. The computing architecture for Fog Computing [FC], Cloud Computing [CC] and, MultiCloud Computing [MCC] are compared, and their limitations are given. Several group researchers used this Edge Computing to develop an EC based application, and they achieved

their goals. The two new emerging technologies Fog computing and Edge computing provide the better QoS [Quality of Service] to IoT applications are reached and explained [17].

Big Data

Big Data is defined as an extreme amount of indefinite data in a variety of formats generated from a variety of sources with rapid speed in order to provide statistical results that are beneficial to the business or an industry.

Big Data Definition By Gartner - “Big Data is high-volume, velocity and variety information assets that demand cost -effective, innovative forms of information processing for enhanced insight and decision making”

Big Data Values

Data itself is quite often inconsequential in its own right. Big Data characteristics are defined popularly using the four V’s.: volume, velocity, variety, and veracity. These four characteristics provide multiple dimensions to the value of data at hand.

Characteristics of Big Data

In 2001, Gartner accidentally aided a fall of echo with an article that forecast trends in the industry, gathering them under the headings Data Volume, Data Velocity, and Data Variety. This inflation continues in its inevitable march, and about a decade later we had 4 V’s of Big Data, then 7 V’s and then 10 V’s. Now we are having 42 V’s of Big Data and Data Science which are developed by some researchers

Big Data and Its Evolutions

Smart Data: Beyond the volume and towards the reality

Profligate data: Speed and agility for responsiveness

Big Data Analytics: Making smooth resolutions and predictions

Amorphous data: Adding meaning and importance

Big Data Architecture

Big Data architecture is designed to handle the breakdown, handling, and scrutiny of data that is too

large or compound for the outdated database systems. The edge at which organizations enter into the Big Data empire differs, depending on the capabilities of the users and their tools. As the trappings are advanced for working with Big Data sets, the extraction of getting values are obtained through advanced analytics.

Big Data solutions involve one or more of the following types of workload:

Batch processing of Big Data sources at rest. Hadoop is mainly motivated on batch data processing. An example is payroll and billing systems.

Real-time processing of Big Data in motion. Examples are Radar systems, customer services, and bank ATMs.

Interactive Exploration of Big Data: Now it became a significant ingredient of discovery-oriented applications in diverse areas, including scientific computing, financial analysis, evidence-based medicine and genomics. Predictive analytics and machine learning.

Predictive Analytics: It is the branch of the advanced analytics which is used to make predictions about unknown future events. Example of predictive analytics is credit scoring.

Machine Learning: It is a new branch of programming and is considered an evolving technology used to enable computers to analyze a set of data and learn from the insights gathered. Examples of machine learning include classification models, recommendation engines, etc.

In future, some challenges are need to be tackled by the researcher while designing the architecture style. They are: Storing and processing of large volumes of data in a traditional database, Transforming unstructured data for inquiry and reporting. Detention, development, and evaluate unbounded streams of data in real time, or with low latency.

Comparison of Big Data Architectures

Lambda Architecture

The lambda architecture, first proposed by Nathan Marz, addresses the problem of identifying latency while large datasets are processed by some algorithms in real time. For example, the algorithm such as MapReduce is used to route the data in a

parallel manner across this systems architecture. So this architecture creates to a new path for data flow. All data coming into the system goes through these two paths:

1. A batch layer (cold track) stores all the incoming data in its raw form and performs batch processing on the data. This result is stored as a batch view.
2. A speed layer (hot path) analyses data in real time. This layer is designed for low latency, at the outflow of precision.

A drawback to the lambda architecture is its complication. Processing logic appears in two different spaces — the cold and hot paths — using different frameworks. This structure leads to duplicate computation logic and the complexity of managing the architecture for both ways.

Kappa Architecture

The Kappa architecture was proposed by Jay Kreps, which has the same goals as the lambda architecture, but with an important distinction: All data flows through a single path, using the stream processing system. Similar to the lambda architecture's batch layer, event data is immutable, and it is collected by, instead of a subset. The documents are ingested by a stream of events into a distributed and fault-tolerant unified log. These events are ordered by, and the current state of an event is changed only by a new experience being appended. When related to speed layer, all event processing is performed on the input stream and continued as a real-time vision.

Recomputed the entire data set is required (equivalent to what the batch layer does in lambda), replay the stream, using parallelism to complete the computation in a timely fashion. Throughout the different architectures to Big Data processing, the principal of data procurement boils down to gathering data from distributed information sources with the intention of storing them in accessible and capable data storage. To achieve the above goal the succeeding three main components are required:

Protocols that allow the gathering of information from distributed data sources of any type (unstructured, semi-structured, structured data) m, Contexts with which the data is collected from the distributed sources by using different protocols, Technologies that allow the determined storage of the data retrieved by the Frameworks.

Phases of the Big Data Data Generation

It is the first step of Big Data. It is large scale, highly diverse and complex datasets generated through longitudinal and distributed data sources. Such data stores include sensors, videos, click streams, and all other available data sources.

Data Acquisition

It refers to the process of gathering, filtering, and cleaning data before the data is placed into a data warehouse or any other storage solution. The acquisition of Big Data was most commonly governed by four V's: volume, velocity, variety, and value. Most data acquisition scenarios assume high-volume, high-velocity, and high-variety. But low-value data have flexible and time-efficient gathering, filtering, and cleaning algorithms that ensure only high-value fragments of the data, which are processed by the data-warehouse.

Data Storage

Data storage is the footage (storing) of information (data) in a storage medium. Electronic data storage requires electrical power to store and retrieve data. Data storage in a format of digital (or) machine-readable medium is sometimes called as digital data. Examples of machine-readable data on papers include Barcodes and magnetic ink character recognition (MICR).

Data Analysis

It is a process of examining, cleaning, and exhibiting data with the goal of discovering useful information, informing conclusions and supporting decision-making. Data analysis technique such as "Mining", focuses on displaying and knowledge discovery for analytical rather than purely descriptive purposes. But business intelligence covers data analysis that relies heavily on accumulation, which focuses mainly on business statistics.

Sources of Big Data

Big Data sources are repositories of large volumes of data. Using business intelligence applications like Logi Info, users can quickly connect to and derive value from these sources. This application brings more information to users' presentations without

requiring the data, while that data be held in a single repository or by cloud vendor registered data store.

Examples of Big Data sources are Amazon Redshift, HP Vertica, and MongoDB. Emerging Big Data sources are analytic/columnar data stores, NoSQL, and Hadoop data.

Some of the foremost sources of Big Data are listed as follows:

Sensors/meters and activity records from electronic devices
Social interactions

Business transactions
Electronic Files
Broadcastings

The other examples of Big Data sources and their corresponding mining techniques are as follows:

1. Social network profiles
2. Social influencers
3. Activity-generated data
4. Hadoop MapReduce application results
5. Legacy documents
6. Software as a Service (SaaS)
7. Public
8. Data warehouse appliances
9. Columnar/NoSQL data sources
10. Network and in-stream monitoring technologies

Big Data Analytics

The concept of Big Data has been around for years; most organizations now understand that if they capture all the data that streams into their businesses, they can apply analytics and get significant value from it. But even in the 1950s, decades before anyone uttered the term "Big Data," businesses were using basic analytics (essential numbers in a spreadsheet that were examined by manual process) to uncover insights and trends.

The new benefits that Big Data analytics brings to the table are speed and efficiency. Whereas a few years ago a business would have gathered information, run analytics and unearthed information that could be used by business for future decisions. Today that business can identify insights for immediate decisions. The ability to work faster and stay agile gives organizations a competitive edge they didn't have before. Figure 4 shows Big Data and Big Data Analytics architecture.

Fig 4: Big Data and Big Data Analytics Framework

Why Big Data Analytics is Important?

Big Data analytics helps organizations (or) businesses to couple their data and use it to identify new prospects, which leads to smarter business moves, more efficient operations, higher profits, and happier customers.

Cost reduction, Faster and better decision making, new products and services, Applications of Big Data Analytics, Travel and Hospitality, Health care, Government and Retail.

Big Data Analytics and IOT

In today’s world, many people would believe that the concept of Big Data analytics was no more different from the notion of the Internet of things, as, “Like the fish different from the water it swims in”. Both these concepts being big names in the industry have some significant differences among them, these differences only exist very much for the boosting of various systems and operations of a company.

Big Data analytics solely fall under the umbrella term for the Internet of Things, which refers to all those technological devices that have made the world, a closer and a better place today. One of the key differences between these two is “fact” that these two concepts revolve around things that are somewhat different from each other. When it comes to Internet of Things, they revolve around solutions. It is an arrangement with all the various devices and services that help in offering assured solutions.

The time constraints faced by both concepts. 233 The massive data projects consist of solutions, especially where the data is allowed to sit for almost a

day or two. Then once it has settled properly, this data is then used to help sort out things regarding all the analysis that is conducted 237. This 238 is the reason why usually it is the 234 characteristic 239 support systems which give out the long duration scenarios like capacity building, predictive maintenance and 241 revenue protection. On the other hand Internet of Things usually ends up supporting of the real-time use scenarios such as real-time ad bidding, operational optimization, and detection of security breaches as well as fraud detection and so on.

Data analytics usually derives all of its data from various sources, 240 which comes from the interaction between human generation and its information. These sources include social media activity, emails, pictures uploaded and much more. On the other hand, the internet of things doesn’t use these human-generated sources but unquestionably uses aggregation and compression of great amounts of machine-generated data that comes to us from a range of sensors like Fitness Trackers, RFIDs and VR devices and so on. 242

Data Lakes for Big Data Analytics

Data lakes are repositories where organizations strategically gather and store all the data they need to analyze to reach a specific goal. The nature and format of the data may be semi-structured, structured, and unstructured data. The data lake is what organizations need for Big Data Analytics in a mixed environment of data. However, there are challenges to this model as well where Hadoop is a well-known solutions player and data lakes as we know it, that these are not an universal answer for all analytics needs.

Big Data Analytics - Use Cases

- Qubole Data Service (QDS)
- Sentiment Analysis
- 360-degree customer View
- Ad-hoc Analysis
- Real-time Analytics
- Multi-Channel Marketing
- Customer Micro-Segmentation
- Ad Fraud Detection
- Click Stream Analysis

Benefits of Big Data Analytics

Evaluating Big Data security analytics platforms, consider five factors that are essential to realizing the full benefits of Big Data analytics.

The Unified Data Management Platform

It is the foundation of a Big Data security analytics system that stores and queries originality data. For example, it is trying to implement distributed versions of some features of databases which include ACID transactions as well. It must balance both cost and scalability.

Support for Multiple Data Types

Big Data security analytics controls the scalability of Big Data platforms with the inquiry abilities of security analytics and SIEM tools.

Scalable Data Ingestion

By maintaining a high write throughput of queuing data in a message queue systems can accommodate scalable data ingestion. Instead, the data management system may keep a file that acts as a buffer to hold data while it is written to disk.

Security Analytic Tools

Big Data platforms such as Hadoop and Spark are general-purpose tools and these are used for building security analytical tools, but these two are not security analytical tools for themselves.

Compliance Reporting

It is no longer a “nice to have” requirement. If it is required, review the reporting commands included with various Big Data security platforms to confirm the needs of your business are met.

The World’s First Open-Source & Massively Parallel Data Platform -GREENPLUM

The Database is an advanced, fully featured, open sourcedata platform. It provides powerful and rapid analytics on petabyte-scale data volumes. Distinctively geared toward Big Data analytics, Greenplum Database was powered by the world’s most advanced cost-based query optimizer delivering high analytical query performance on large volumes of data. The Greenplum Database project was released under the Apache 2 license. This database architecture provides automatic parallelization of all

data and queries in a scale-out architecture. High-performance loading uses MPP [Massive Parallel Processing] technology. Loading speeds scale with each additional node to greater than ten terabytes per hour, per rack. The query optimizer available in Greenplum Database is the industry’s first cost-based query optimizer for Big Data workloads. It can scale interactive and batch mode analytics to large datasets in the petabytes without degrading query performance and throughput. The data is accessed by the way of organizing table or partition storage, implementation, and compression. Users have the choice of row or column-oriented storage and processing for any table or partition. Apache Madlib, a library for scalable in-database analytics, which extend the SQL capabilities of Greenplum Database through user-defined functions. Access and query processing of all data is done through the external table syntax. Traditional on-premises and next-generation public data lakes are supported by this data platform.

Big Data Challenges

Hadoop is Hard

Apache Hadoop is one of the Big Data tools used to handle enormous capacities of structured and unstructured data. Hadoop commonly requires wide-ranging internal resources to maintain, and many companies are left dedicating most of their resources to the technology rather than to the actual Big Data problem.

Scalability

With Big Data, it’s crucial to be able to scale up and down on-demand. Many organizations fail to take into account how quickly a Big Data project can grow and evolve.

Continuously squeezing a project is to add extra resources cuts into time for data analysis. Big Data workloads also tend to be burst, makes it difficult to forecast where resources should be allocated. The extent of this Big Data challenge varies by the solution. A solution in the cloud will scale much at ease and faster than an on-premises solution.

Lack of Talent

Businesses are feeling the data talent shortage. Because there is a lack of data scientists and team

members for the successful implementation of Big Data projects, and analysts who have sufficient amount of domain knowledge to identify the valuable insights. Many Big Data vendors seek to overcome this Big Data challenge by providing their educational resources or by providing the bulk of the management.

Actionable Insights

Having extra data doesn't necessarily lead to actionable insights. A key challenge for data science teams is to identify a strong business independent and the proper data sources to collect and analyze to meet that objective. The task doesn't stop there; however. Once key patterns have been identified by the business people, businesses must be prepared to act and make necessary changes to derive business value from them.

Data Quality

Data quality is not a new concern, but the ability to store every piece of data in its unique form from a corporate that complexes the problem. Common causes of cloudy data that must be addressed by the professionals include user input errors, duplicate data, and incorrect data linking. Big Data algorithms can also be used to help data cleaning process.

Security

It concerns about vast lake of data secure. This is a major Big Data challenge. It includes

User authentication for every team and team members accessing the data. Next it relies on restricting access based on a user's need.

Cost Management

It's difficult to project the cost of a Big Data project, and given how quickly they scale, can fast eat up resources. The challenge lies in taking into account all costs of the project from acquiring new hardware/ topaying a cloud provider, to hiring additional personnel. Businesses pursuing on-premises projects must remember the cost of training, maintenance, and expansion. Big Data in the cloud projects must carefully evaluate the service-level settlement with the provider to determine how usage will be billed by it and if there will be any surplus fees.

IOT and Big Data

This disruptive technology needs new infrastructures, including software and hardware applications as well as an OS; enterprises must handle the influx of data that begins flowing in and examine it in real-time as it evolves by the minute. That is where big data arrives into the picture; big data analytics tools can handle large volumes of data generated from IoT devices that create a continuous stream of information. But, to differentiate between them, IoT provides data from which big data analytics can extract evidence to generate perceptions required of it.

The Role of IOT in Big Data

There are many examples of big data and IoT working well together to offer analysis and insight. One such example was represented by the shipping organizations. They have been utilizing big data analytics and sensor data to improve efficiency, save money and lower their environmental impact. They operate sensors on their delivery vehicles to monitor engine health, number of stops, mileage, miles per gallon, and speed.

IOT and big data are creating waves in big agriculture. In this area, the field connects systems monitors to the moisture levels and transmits this data to farmers over a wireless connection. This data will enable farmers to find out when crops are reaching the optimum moisture levels. The applications of IoT and big data concepts in the field of HR enhance throughput and value. Some of the advantages here are improved the selection of talents and job matching with the required personality skills and traits. According to a survey by business people, it is evident that both Big Data Analytics and IoT have a main role to play in HR management.

However, IoT conducts data on a completely different scale, so the analytics solution must accommodate its needs of processing and rapid ingestion followed by a fast and accurate extraction.

There are many solutions available that provide near real-time analytics on large-sized datasets, and necessarily change a full-rack database into a small server that processes up to 100 TB. So small amount of hardware is needed. The analytics database of next-generation leverages GPU technology, thus enabling

even more downsizing of the hardware, i.e. 5 TB on a laptop or a big database in the car. It mostly helps IoT organizations associate the evolving number of data sets, which helps them familiarize to changing trends and attain real-time responses, solving the challenge regarding size and cooperating on the performance.

Conclusion

“Big IoT- Data” – Make the world realistic and proximity digitized paradigm. This paper presented the overall discussion of Big Data and Data Analytics components. The architecture presented here would be better to grasp the underlying techniques using Big Data. The components are unique, and each one is described based on its underlying technology. Here all the technologies with its structures in the context of Big Data and Big data Analytics paradigm are detailed. These ideas will induce the new incoming researcher to do their research work within the field. So there is a tremendous increment in the technology must happen, which leads to overcoming all the challenges are experienced now in the BIG DATA and BIG DATA ANALYTICS ERA. Because of this new technology “Big Data”, every organization must have the capability to the better decision-making process to improve their business in this competitive world. Not only for an organization, is every field benefited in future by this Big IoT era.

BIG DATA and BIG DATA ANALYTICS is used to handle large amount of heterogeneous sensor data generated by many devices in the digitized world. Big Data Analytics is also capable of handling existing data mining techniques as well as new techniques from Apache Hadoop platform provided by the Big Data environment. The process of discovering new procedures with a simple algorithm is possible in this Big Data framework because by 2025 most of the devices are connected to the world of the internet.

Acknowledgments

Our sincere thanks to, who have contributed towards the development of this research paper.

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